

THE ROLE OF MASS MEDIA IN BUILDING NEW UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13832803>

Abstract. *The article is devoted to the problem of turning mass media into a powerful factor in the formation of social values. Our society is experiencing a decisive historical stage of the formation of market relations. These new needs lead to new values. The process of formation of social values by mass media can be divided into three stages: synthesis, analysis and inclusion. By creating and conveying new values, modern mass media have a significant impact on the formation of not only public opinion, but also the outlook of all social strata of society.*

Keywords: *information and communication technologies, mass media, space in Uzbekistan, online media, civil society.*

Today, we are witnessing important processes occurring in the field of information exchange in the context of global integration. The emergence of the Internet in the modern world marked the beginning of a unique and vast media space where the existence of large or small groups is dominated by speed, regardless of borders and geographic distances. Most importantly, modern information and communication technologies have facilitated the emergence of a new type of mass media—Internet media—that has already been accepted and demanded by society and has a significant impact on it.

The advantages of online mass media are clear: access to the widest audience, efficiency in information processing, and quality. It is noteworthy that the new type of media embodies the unique characteristics of print media, television, and radio (visual, video, and audio). At the same time, online mass media can gather feedback from viewers in almost every corner of the world in real-time. Moreover, viewers are not only able to express their opinions about the distributed information but also have the opportunity to add new details and expand the information (in forums and comments, you can often read or see interesting things—vivid details of the described event).

In short, modern technologies have liberated both journalists and information consumers. From this, one can agree with the idea that internet media are the most democratic forms of mass communication. However, such rapid development of the Internet has intensified information relations. As Fomicheva I.D. noted, nowhere else (except the Internet) can you easily transfer someone else's content as if it were your own, using third parties, five times, and so on.

There is some truth to this perspective, but those who claim the opposite also have their serious arguments: everything on the Internet is mass media. These opposing views lead to the question: how do we qualify information resources on the network? Social networks have indeed become a space for communication and debates today, making it difficult to label them as mass media.

Another aspect is the activity of specialized online publications that have absorbed all the functions of mass media and operate on a professional basis. It is essential to clearly understand the presence of mass media in the context of information distributed via the Internet. Another characteristic of new media is that information technologies are primarily in the hands of consumers. As the Spanish urban sociologist M. Castells wrote, new information technologies are

not only tools that need to be used but also processes that must be developed. Users and creators can unite as one entity. Thus, the abundance of modern communication has increased risks while also providing unique opportunities for both development and the most radical regression of humanity.

The role of media in developing a country is multifaceted and crucial for various aspects of societal progress. Here are some key points highlighting this role:

1) Information Dissemination

- Media serves as a primary source of information for the public about government policies, health initiatives, and social issues.

- It helps raise awareness about important topics such as education, healthcare, and economic development.

2) Education and Literacy

- Educational programs and content can improve literacy rates and knowledge about various subjects.

- Media can provide access to educational resources, particularly in remote areas.

3) Promoting Civic Engagement

- Media encourages citizen participation in governance and civic activities.

- It provides a platform for public discourse, enabling citizens to voice their opinions and concerns.

4) Economic Development

- Media plays a role in advertising and promoting local businesses, contributing to economic growth.

- It can attract foreign investment by highlighting opportunities and developments in the country.

5) Cultural Exchange and Identity

- Media helps preserve and promote cultural heritage and identity.

- It fosters understanding and appreciation of diverse cultures within the country.

6) Accountability and Transparency

- Investigative journalism holds governments and organizations accountable, reducing corruption.

- Media serves as a watchdog, ensuring that public officials act in the interest of the citizens.

7) Social Change

- Media can challenge societal norms and promote social justice issues, such as gender equality and human rights.

- It amplifies voices of marginalized communities, fostering inclusivity.

8) Public Health Awareness

- Media campaigns can inform the public about health issues, preventive measures, and available resources.

- Especially crucial during health crises, such as pandemics, to disseminate accurate information.

In summary, media is an essential tool for communication, education, and empowerment. It fosters development by promoting informed citizenry, encouraging economic growth, and facilitating social change, ultimately contributing to a more progressive and resilient society.

Currently, debates continue about whether traditional mass media will make way for the Internet. Researchers note that a portion of the audience for print media is stopping reading newspapers and switching to information available online, while many television viewers are also transitioning to the Internet. Experts in modern information and communication technologies emphasize that traditional information sources will ultimately be replaced by the Internet.

Thus, digital expert E. Volkov firmly believes that print media will continue to decline, with newspapers becoming necessary only as a status symbol. In his view, mobile phone usage will continue to grow. Additionally, the directive nature of television content delivery and the natural loss of viewers will also lead to a decrease in traditional media. According to the expert, the future lies in direct channels for delivering content, such as neural networks and messengers that form "personal media."

We can agree with these conclusions regarding the lower effectiveness of traditional mass media compared to electronic media. Based on their distinctive characteristics, newspapers need to be printed, stories must be edited for television and radio, while online publications provide news almost immediately as it becomes available, reporting on events as they unfold (showing them). This is development in an online context, meaning nearly real-time. This is certainly a significant advantage of online publications; however, it should be noted that they will only be in demand if they meet certain requirements: effectiveness, objectivity, quality text, and good video and photography.

In this regard, questions arise about the unique characteristics of a journalist's activities in this information space, as well as the main trends. In this information space, the journalist's role involves understanding the main trends related to political institutions, processes, and technologies, the development of Internet journalism, the genre specificity and thematic direction of publications in the World Wide Web, and methods for attracting users' attention. It seems significant that the Internet has opened new opportunities and has become a unique catalyst for the development of civic journalism.

As A. Sveshnikov wrote, "Civic journalism is journalism that is sensitive to all the needs of society, encompassing the moods of all its layers; if you will, it is a social barometer. Its activity vector is multifaceted: on one hand, it informs citizens about how power operates... On the other hand, civic journalism analyzes processes occurring at the core of societal life, whether political, economic, or otherwise. Thirdly, it provides a means for state institutions to engage with the entire civil society and social institutions through the press, ensuring feedback" [7].

All of these conditions easily align with the working format of Internet media. Accordingly, the new media space opens up broad opportunities for journalists and, in general, for mass media to operate effectively as an institution of civil society, influencing socio-political processes. In this context, N.Yu. Leskonog points out that Internet technologies are increasingly becoming an important communication tool aimed at enhancing the political activity of youth. He emphasizes the need for political leaders, political parties, and social-political organizations to ensure that their policies are supported by information, manage content published online, and deliver prompt, high-quality, and meaningful feedback to young people.

Thus, the positive aspects of mass media's influence on youth include the following:

1. ****Speed of Information Acquisition****: Mass media possesses the ability to provide information quickly. As a result, young people become aware of everything happening around them, thereby satisfying the "information hunger."

2. ****Intellectual Development****: Mass media contributes to both general and specific knowledge growth.

3. ****Mutual Awareness****: In other words, mass media has the function of facilitating information exchange between authorities and the population.

Among the negative factors, it is important to highlight that mass media has ceased to be a positive source of information for many, with propaganda taking precedence. Today, the availability of information leads to numerous problems with psychological characteristics. Mass media begins to impose certain value indicators.

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